

Life, Death & After Life

a moment at DRS Festival of Emergence 2021

by Seda Özçetin, PhD Student @UID & DCODE Network

● 24/7 access

Reflections | September 16, 2021 | CEST 16:00

Tools: Miro, Zoom, Image Processing Tools of Your Choice

Background

This is a moment about things.

Me reading “*Changing Things: The Future of Objects in a Digital World*”
and me learning about the “*DRS Festival of Emergence*” coincided.

And I was like, “hmm, emergence”...

And I was like “what kinds of things have emerged in my life?”

And I was like “hmm, interesting”.

So, I thought maybe there is a moment here that needs to be taken.

What is this Moment?

I have to admit that it has changed over time and I am still a bit confused :)

Simply put, this is a moment of *creative reflection on our things*, which we usually take for granted.

This is a moment to become aware of them, their lives and lifecycles, dynamics behind their life events and transitions, their spatio-temporal ecologies, things for us and things in themselves.

Any Kinds of Things?

Yes.

My research is actually related to fluid assemblages,

but I don't want to limit this moment in that way and rather stay open to see what comes along.

And to be honest, since it is about emergence, one way or another, fluid assemblages will pop-up.

Excuse Me, But What is a Fluid Assemblage?

Simply put, fluid assemblages are networked computational technical artefacts, which come into being in runtime through a constant loop with being used.

“

... the technical artifacts that now exist in our world are more like fluid assemblages than what we traditionally think of as things: assemblages because they are made out of a diverse range of material and immaterial resources both contained within the object as it appears in front of us as well as located elsewhere in the network; fluid because their precise forms are assembled dynamically and thus change continuously.

These are quite different from the stable, predictable things that are the traditional objects of industrial design and focus of theorizing about the artificial. In the ways they are manifested, the functions they serve, and the “user experiences” they support, these fluid assemblages can appear to be quite thing-like. And yet, the interfaces that are engaged in use are only the surfaces that conceal the many layers of code, platforms, systems, and interconnections between them that allow specific instances to come into being as things available for use.

How to Participate in this Moment?

1 Choose one of the activity categories below or define one yourself.

Listening to music

Doing sports

Staying healthy

Cooking and eating

Socializing

Travelling

Working

Taking care of children

Staying organized

How to Participate in this Moment?

2 Think about what kinds of things have emerged, disappeared, reincarnated, or repurposed in relation to these activities.

Interesting things happen at moments of transitions such as moving to another country, buying a new device, starting a new job or school, getting into new social circles, starting a new hobby.

Look at those moments in your life and see if these had an impact on your things or your relations to things.

You can also look through your surroundings and devices as a starting point.

Just to Give a Bit of an Idea:

This is what i will probably tell with my collage

The things that surrounded me have changed dramatically when I moved from Turkey to first Sweden and then to Denmark and then back to Turkey.

A specific example would be about listening to music:

I had a nice collection of CDs and cassettes, but when I moved abroad, I didn't take them with me. In Scandinavia, I would hold myself from buying CD's because it made moving homes more difficult. Instead, first the CD's from the public libraries emerged in my room and then Spotify and Youtube.

As much as I found these fluid assemblages super practical, I didn't like the experience much. They were not very good at getting to know my taste and would make wrong assumptions and boring suggestions. For example, it would suggest me to listen to a Turkish pop singer (a very bad one)

just because I listened to a Turkish classical pianist. Also, when I learned how little Spotify pays to the musicians I gradually stopped using it.

Occasionally for a social gathering I would login for a playlist and it would be refreshed and ready.

When I moved back to Turkey, my CDs and cassettes emerged back into my life. They haven't aged a bit in themselves

but for me some of them were not as exciting any longer. So, I started going back to Youtube for some of my playlists, get transported to my life in Copenhagen, and sometimes would be annoyed to see that they wouldn't be available in my new location.

How to Participate in this Moment?

3 Once you spot something you want to share, tell us the story with a collage and place it on Miro.

Things to Consider While Creating the Collage

Analyze the timeline and the lifecycle.

Who are the characters(human & non-human)?

What kinds of relations are there between these characters?

What kinds of habits are associated with them?

Which events triggered changes?

What are your feelings or thoughts about all this?

Things not to Be Bothered By

Perfection. This is more like a quick & dirty visual storytelling moment.

Trying to Make Sense of Timeline

MOVING ABROAD

MOVING BACK

ME & MY THINGS

a thing that i disgard

my CD
Youtube for me in DK

my CD without me
Youtube for me in DK

Youtube for me in Turkey

my CD

What will I Do with your Contributions and Data?

This is part of my PhD studies. So, I would like to keep the contributions as insights and for further study. If and/or when I want to use your contributions in written, oral, visual works on offline and online mediums, all your information will be anonymized unless you want to be credited.

If you change your mind to be included in this moment, you may request for your work to be deleted by sending me an email through seda.ozcetin@umu.se. It would be nice to know why so that i conduct better moments in the future.

The Miro board will be closed to public access after the festival. If you want to stay on the board, please get in touch via email to receive a passcode.

For any comments or questions, please contact me through seda.ozcetin@umu.se.

Thank you so much for your time!
Hope you enjoyed this moment!